

with the hydrochloride of 2:6-dihydroxy-4-isopropylpyridine (V) (Gibson and Simonsen, *loc. cit.*) which was formed in prepondering amount.

Following Bland and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 856) the *trans* configuration has been assigned to the above acid. With acetyl chloride the *trans*-acid gave the hydroxy anhydride (VI) which on treatment with 30% potassium hydroxide furnished the *cis*-acid (?). Water decomposed the hydroxy anhydride, however, into the *trans*-acid (*cf.* Bland and Thorpe, *loc. cit.*). The conversion of the *cis*-acid into the *trans*-isomer has not been effected, owing to lack of sufficient material.

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

Ethyl *isobutyryl*malonate (Knoevenagel and Faber, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2770) does not condense with ethyl cyanoacetate to yield ethyl α -cyano- β -*isobutyryl*- γ -carbomethoxyglutaconate.

EXPERIMENTAL.

isoButyryl Chloride.—A good yield of the substance was obtained by the following method. To the acid (192 g.) cooled at 0°, phosphorus trichloride (200 g.) was added gradually. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature, after which it was heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. The acid chloride was decanted from the phosphorus acid and fractionally distilled, b.p. 85-88°/680 mm., yield of twice distilled product being 220 g.

Ethyl isoButyrylacetate.—Some preliminary attempts were made to prepare the substance by the application of the method of Fischer, Goldschmidt and Nussler (*Annalen*, 1931, 486, 31) for the preparation of ethyl *n*-butyrylacetate. The method involves separation and purification from ethyl acetoacetate by fractional distillation. It was, however, found impracticable in the present case, a mixture of ethyl *isobutyryl*acetate and ethyl acetoacetate being invariably formed, which could not be separated by fractional distillation.

The following process was adopted (*cf.* Bouveault and Bongert, *loc. cit.*). To molecular sodium (46 g.), suspended in anhydrous ether (1 litre), freshly distilled ethyl acetoacetate (160 g.) was added dropwise under cooling. To the sodium salt *isobutyryl* chloride (213 g.) was added dropwise, care being taken to see that the temperature never

rose above 0° . After the addition, the product was allowed to stand overnight, and was then decomposed with water. The ethereal layer was separated, dried and ether removed from it. The residue was repeatedly extracted with 50-70 c.c. portions of ice-cold 9% sodium hydroxide solution till the extract showed no longer any increase in volume (12 times). The united alkaline extract was once extracted with ether, after which it was decomposed with hydrochloric acid. The oil that separated was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water and then dried and ether removed. The residue was distilled when ethyl *C-isobutyryl*acetate boiled at $100^{\circ}/6$ mm., yield 107 g. This was shaken up with 10% ammonium hydroxide (200 c.c.) for 20 minutes after which the mixture was warmed on the water-bath at 40° for 25 minutes to complete the reaction. The oily layer was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water, aqueous sodium bicarbonate (2 times), and again with water, then dried and ether removed. The residue was distilled in vacuum. Ethyl *isobutyryl* acetate boiled at $72^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 70.5 g.

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the cold, melted at 103° . (Found: N, 19.7. $C_{19}H_{17}O_3N_3$ requires N, 19.5 per cent).

Ethyl α -Cyano- β -isopropylglutaconate (IV).—Ethyl *iso-butyryl*acetate was condensed with ethyl sodiocyanoacetate according to the method of Rogerson and Thorpe (*loc. cit.*). The yield of the ester (IV) was exceedingly low. A cold solution of potassium (13 g.) in absolute alcohol (150 c.c.) was mixed with ethyl cyanoacetate (37.6 g.) with shaking, and the potassium derivative was cooled to 0° and treated with ethyl *isobutyryl*acetate (52 g.) and the whole kept in a freezing mixture for 6 hours and then at room temperature for 3 days with occasional shaking. The potassium derivative of the original ester dissolved and gave place to that of the condensation product. It was decomposed with water, the red coloured solution acidified with hydrochloric acid and the oily layer that separated was taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed thoroughly with sodium carbonate solution, water, and ether removed. The residue [ethyl α -cyano- β -isopropylglutaconate (IV)] distilled at $145^{\circ}/3$ mm., as a colourless viscid oil, yield 1.3 g. (36 g. of ethyl *isobutyryl* acetate were recovered). (Found: C, 61.5; H, 7.5; N, 5.5. d_{25}^{25} , 1.0588. $C_{18}H_{19}O_4$ requires C, 61.7; H, 7.5; N, 5.5 per cent).

Hydrolysis of Ethyl α -Cyano- β -isopropylglutaconate : Formation of 2:6-Dihydroxy-4-isopropylpyridine (V).—In a typical experiment, the ester (2 g.) was mixed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (6 c.c.) and heated under reflux on a sand-bath. After 4 hours, hydrochloric acid (4 c.c.) was added

and the heating continued for another 4 hours. The product was then evaporated to one-third its bulk, when the hydrochloride of 2:6-dihydroxy-4-isopropylpyridine separated (1.1 g.). This was filtered, the hydrochloride suspended in water, made first alkaline with ammonia and then the solution acidified with acetic acid when the free base was deposited. It recrystallised from absolute alcohol in colourless rectangular prisms, m.p. 213-14° (Gibson and Simonsen, *loc. cit.* give m.p. 213-14°). In its properties, it entirely agreed with those described by Gibson and Simonsen. It gives a purple colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. An aqueous solution rapidly turns green in air, whilst an ammoniacal solution becomes blue. (Found: N, 9.7. $C_8H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 9.2 per cent).

trans-β-isoPropylglutaconic Acid (I).—The mother-liquor from the above experiment after the filtration of the hydrochloride, was further concentrated, and then repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried over magnesium sulphate and ether removed, when crude *trans-β-iso*propylglutaconic acid solidified (0.1 g.). Repeated crystallisations from a mixture of petroleum ether and acetone gave rectangular plates, m.p. 142°. It is easily soluble in water, alcohol, acetone and sparingly soluble in chloroform and benzene. [Found: C, 55.89, 55.77; H, 7.0, 7.12. Equiv., 85.5, 86.6. $C_8H_{12}O_6$ (dibasic) requires C, 55.82; H, 7.39 per cent. Equiv., 86.]

Conversion of the Above Acid into its Hydroxy Anhydride.—The acid (0.1 g.) was mixed with acetyl chloride (0.5 c.c.) and the mixture warmed on the water-bath for 15 minutes. After the removal of the excess of acetyl chloride in *vacuo* the anhydride remained as an oil which did not solidify. It gives an intense purple colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride which disappears on warming.

On mixing benzene solutions of the anhydride and *p*-toluidine, the semi-*p*-toluidide separated in prismatic needles, m.p. 150°.

Conversion of the Anhydride into the cis-Acid.—The anhydride (0.1 g.) was mixed with aqueous caustic potash (30% 1.5 c.c.) and warmed on the water-bath at 35° for 3 hours. The product was acidified with hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether (4 times), the ethereal solution dried and ether removed, when the residue solidified. It was recrystallised from acetone, m.p. 129.5-130.5°. [Found: Equiv., 85. $C_8H_{12}O_6$ (dibasic) requires Equiv., 86].

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